

Expanding Newton Mechanics with Neutrosophy and Quad-stage Method —New Newton Mechanics Taking Law of Conservation of Energy as Unique Source Law

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Abstract. Neutrosophy is a new branch of philosophy, and "Quad-stage" (Four stages) is the expansion of Hegel's triad thesis, antithesis, synthesis of development. Applying Neutrosophy and "Quad-stage" method, the purposes of this paper are expanding Newton Mechanics and making it become New Newton Mechanics (NNW) taking law of conservation of energy as unique source law. In this paper the examples show that in some cases other laws may be contradicted with the law of conservation of energy. The original Newton's three laws and the law of gravity, in principle can be derived by the law of conservation of energy. Through the example of free falling body, this paper derives the original Newton's second law by using the law of conservation of energy, and proves that there is not the contradiction between the original law of gravity and the law of conservation of energy; and through the example of a small ball rolls along the inclined plane (belonging to the problem cannot be solved by general relativity that a body is forced to move in flat space), derives improved Newton's second law and improved law of gravity by using law of conservation of energy. Whether or not other conservation laws (such as the law of conservation of momentum and the law of conservation of angular momentum) can be utilized, should be tested by law of conservation of energy. When the original Newton's second law is not correct, then the

laws of conservation of momentum and angular momentum are no longer correct; therefore the general forms of improved law of conservation of momentum and improved law of conservation of angular momentum are presented. In the cases that law of conservation of energy cannot be used effectively, New Newton Mechanics will not exclude that according to other theories or accurate experiments to derive the laws or formulas to solve some specific problems. For example, with the help of the result of general relativity, the improved Newton's formula of universal gravitation can be derived, which can be used to solve the problem of advance of planetary perihelion and the problem of deflection of photon around the Sun. Again, according to accurate experimental result, the synthesized gravitational formula (including the effects of other celestial bodies and sunlight pressure) for the problem of deflection of photon around the Sun is presented. Unlike the original Newton Mechanics, in New Newton Mechanics, for different problems, may have different laws of motion, different formulas of gravity, as well as different expressions of energy. For example, for the problem of a small ball rolls along the inclined plane, and the problem of advance of planetary perihelion, the two formulas of gravity are completely different.

Keywords: Neutrosophy, "Quad-stage" (Four stages), law of conservation of energy, unique source law, New Newton Mechanics

1 Introduction

As a new branch of philosophy, Neutrosophy studies the origin, nature, and scope of neutralities, as well as their interactions with different ideational spectra. According to Neutrosophy that there is a 3D Neutrosophic Space, where each dimension of the space represents respectively the

truth (T), the falsehood (F), and the indeterminacy (I) of the statement under consideration. More information about Neutrosophy may be found in references [1,2]. Quad-stage is introduced in reference [3], it is the expansion of Hegel's triad-stage (triad thesis, antithesis, synthesis of development). The four stages are "general theses", "general antitheses", "the most important and the most

complicated universal relations”, and “general syntheses”. In quad-stage method, “general theses” may be considered as the notion or idea <A> in neutrosophy; “general antitheses” may be considered as the notion or idea <Anti-A> in neutrosophy; “the most important and the most complicated universal relations” may be considered as the notion or idea <Neut-A> in neutrosophy; and “general syntheses” are the final results. The different kinds of results in the above mentioned four stages can also be classified and induced with the viewpoints of neutrosophy. Thus, the theory and achievement of neutrosophy can be applied as many as possible, and the method of quad-stage will be more effective. The combination of Neutrosophy and quad-stage will be a powerful method to realize many innovations in areas of science, technology, literature and art. Therefore, this paper expands Newton Mechanics with Neutrosophy and Quad-stage Method and creates New Newton Mechanics (NNW) taking law of conservation of energy as unique source law.

One of the development trends of natural science is using fewer laws to solve increasing problems. In this process, according to the viewpoint of neutrosophy, some laws will play the increasingly great roles; some laws will play the smaller roles, or even disappear from the ranks of laws; and the middle ones will be improved and expanded to play the greater roles.

As expanding Newton mechanics with neutrosophy and quad-stage, the whole process can be divided into the following four stages.

The first stage (stage of “general theses”), for the beginning of development, the thesis (namely Newton mechanics) should be widely, deeply, carefully and repeatedly contacted, explored, analyzed, perfected and so on.

Regarding the advantages of Newton mechanics, that will not be repeated here, while we should stress the deficiencies of Newton mechanics.

As well-known, Newton mechanics cannot be used to solve the problem of advance of planetary perihelion and the problem of deflection of photon around the Sun. For other perspectives on Newton mechanics, we will discuss in detail below, in order to avoid duplication.

The second stage, for the appearance of opposite (antithesis), the antithesis should be also widely, deeply, carefully and repeatedly contacted, explored, analyzed, perfected and so on.

There are many opposites (antitheses) to Newton mechanics. For example: special and general theory of relativity, “theory of everything”, law of conservation of energy, and so on, this paper focuses on the problems related to law of conservation of energy.

The third stage is the one that the most important and the most complicated universal relations. The purpose of this provision stage is to establish the universal relations in the widest scope.

To link and combine Newton mechanics with law of

conservation of energy, as well as the brilliant achievements of modern science and technology, then Newton mechanics can be expanded and developed effectively and successfully in the maximum area.

The fourth stage, to carry on the unification and synthesis regarding various opposites and the suitable pieces of information, factors, and so on; and reach one or more results to expand Newton mechanics which are the best or agreed with some conditions; this is the stage of “general syntheses”.

Now we discuss the law of conservation of energy. Its main contents are as follows: In a closed system, the total energy of this system remains unchanged.

Because the law of conservation of energy is the most important one in natural sciences, it should play an increasingly great role. For this reason and according to the principle of the uniqueness of truth, this paper presents the New Newton Mechanics (NNM) taking law of conservation of energy as unique source law with Neutrosophy and Quad-stage Method.

In the area of Newton Mechanics, there should be one truth only. Other so-called truth, either it can be derived by the unique truth, or we can prove that in certain cases it is not true. As well-known, when Newton founded the classical mechanics, four laws were proposed, they were Newton's three laws and the law of gravity. If the law of conservation of energy is choosing as the unique source law, that in principle, all the Newton's four laws can be derived according to the law of conservation of energy; after studying carefully we found that this may indeed be the real case. In addition, in the areas such as physics, mechanics, engineering and so on, there are three very important laws: the law of conservation of energy, the law of conservation of momentum and the law of conservation of angular momentum. If we believe that the law of conservation of energy is the truth, then for the law of conservation of momentum and the law of conservation of angular momentum, either they can be derived by the law of conservation of energy, or we can prove that in certain cases they are not true. We believe that the true situation is the latter, namely, the law of conservation of momentum and the law of conservation of angular momentum are not true in some cases (or their results are contradicted to the law of conservation of energy). Of course, we can also find that in some cases, these two laws still can be used. Taking the example that a man walks along the car located on the horizontal smooth rail, we can see that at present in the area of Newton mechanics, some people do not notice the case of the contradiction between the law of conservation of energy and the law of conservation of momentum.

2 New three laws of motion and new law of gravity (formula) created by law of conservation of energy for New Newton Mechanics

The original Newton's three laws of motion (partial theses) are as follows.

Newton's First Law of Motion: Every object in a state of uniform motion (or at rest) tends to remain in that state of motion (or at rest) unless an external force is applied to it. For short: rest remains rest, and moving remains moving.

Newton's Second Law of Motion: The relationship between an object's mass m , its acceleration a , and the applied force F is $F = ma$. The direction of the force is the same as the direction of the acceleration.

Newton's Third Law of Motion: For every action there is an equal and opposite reaction.

The original Newton's law of gravity (partial theses): The attractive force between two objects is as follows

$$F = -\frac{GMm}{r^2} \quad (1)$$

While through the stage of "general antitheses" and the stage of "the most important and the most complicated universal relations", for NNM, taking law of conservation of energy as unique source law, then we have the following NNM's three laws of motion and law of gravity.

NNM's First Law of Motion: Every object in a state of uniform motion (or in a state of uniform rotation, or at rest) tends to remain in that state of motion (or in a state of uniform rotation, or at rest) unless an external force is applied to it; otherwise the law of conservation of energy will be destroyed. For short: rest remains rest, moving remains moving, and rotating remains rotating.

NNM's Second Law of Motion: The relationship between an object's mass m , its acceleration a , and the applied force F is a function that should be derived by law of conservation of energy. The direction of the force is the same as the direction of the acceleration. In general, the function can be written as the form of variable dimension fractal: $F = ma^{1+\varepsilon}$, where: ε is a constant or a variable. For different problems, the forms of second law may be different.

NNM's Third Law of Motion: In general, for every action there is an equal and opposite reaction. In special case, the function relationship between action and reaction should be derived by law of conservation of energy. The improved form of the original Newton's

third law ($F_{AB} = -F_{BA}$) is as follows: $F_{AB} = -F_{BA}^{1+\lambda}$, where: λ is a constant or a variable. For different problems, the forms of third law may be different.

NNM's law (formula) of gravity: The attractive force between two objects is a function that should be derived by law of conservation of energy, or experimental data; or derived with the help of other theories. For different problems, the forms of law (formula) of gravity may be different. The results of original Newton's law of gravity are only accurate in the cases that two objects are relative static or running the straight line between one center and another center, and the like; for other cases its results are all approximate. In general, NNM's law (formula) of gravity may be taken as the form that adding the amending term to original Newton's law of gravity, or the following form of variable dimension fractal:

$$F = -\frac{GMm}{r^{2-\delta}} \quad (2)$$

where: δ is a constant or a variable.

Now for an example, a NNM's law (formula) of gravity (an improved Newton's law of gravity) and a NNM's second law of motion (an improved Newton's second law of motion), they are suitable for this example only, are derived simultaneously by law of conservation of energy.

Firstly, through "universal relations", the variational principles established by the law of conservation of energy can be given with least squares method (LSM).

Supposing that the initial total energy of a closed system equals $W(0)$, and for time t the total energy equals $W(t)$, then according to the law of conservation of energy:

$$W(0) = W(t) \quad (3)$$

This can be written as:

$$R_w = \frac{W(t)}{W(0)} - 1 = 0 \quad (4)$$

According to LSM, for the interval $[t_1, t_2]$, we can write the following variational principle:

$$\Pi = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} R_W^2 dt = \min_0 \quad (5)$$

where: \min_0 denotes the minimum value of functional Π and it should be equal to zero.

It should be noted that, in many cases $W(t)$ is approximate, and R_W is not identically equal to zero, therefore Eq.(5) can be used to solve the problem. Besides the time coordinate, another one can also be used. For example, for interval $[x_1, x_2]$, the following variational principle can be given according to the law of conservation of energy:

$$\Pi = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} R_W^2 dx = \min_0 \quad (6)$$

The above-mentioned principles are established by using the law of conservation of energy directly. Sometimes, a certain principle should be established by using the law of conservation of energy indirectly. For example, a special physical quantity Q may be interested, not only it can be calculated by using the law of conservation of energy, but also can be calculated by using other laws (for this paper they are the law of gravity, and Newton's second law). For distinguishing the values, let's denote the value given by other laws as Q , while denote the value given by the law of conservation of energy as Q' , then the value of R_W can be redefined as follows:

$$R_W = \frac{Q}{Q'} - 1 = 0 \quad (7)$$

Substituting Eq. (7) into Eqs. (5) and (6), as Q' is the result calculated with the law of conservation of energy, it gives the variational principle established by using the law of conservation of energy indirectly. Otherwise, it is clear that the extent of the value of Q accords with Q' . Substituting the related quantities into Eq. (5) or Eq. (6), the equations derived by the condition of an extremum can be written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial a_i} = \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial k_i} = 0 \quad (8)$$

After solving these equations, the improved law of gravity, and Newton's second law can be reached at once.

According to the value of Π , the effect of the solution can be judged. The nearer the value of Π is to zero, the better the effect of the solution. It should be noted that besides of solving equations, optimum-seeking methods could also be used for finding the minimum and the constants to be determined. In fact, the optimum seeking method will be used in this paper.

Now we solve an example. As shown in Fig.1, supposing that the small ball rolls along a long incline from A to B. Its initial velocity is zero and the friction and the rotational energy of small ball are neglected.

Fig.1 A small ball rolls from A to B

Supposing that circle O' denotes the Earth, M denotes its mass; m denotes the mass of the small ball (treated as a mass point P), $O'A$ is a plumb line, coordinate x is orthogonal to $O'A$, coordinate y is orthogonal to coordinate x (parallel to $O'A$), BC is orthogonal to $O'A$. The lengths of OA , OB , BC , and AC are all equal to H , and $O'C$ equals the radius R of the Earth. In this example, the value of v_p^2 which is the square of the velocity for the ball located at point P is investigated. To distinguish the quantities, denote the value given by the improved law of gravity and improved Newton's second law as v_p^2 , while $v_p'^2$ denotes the value given by the law of conservation of energy, then Eq. (6) can be written as

$$\Pi = \int_{-H}^0 \left(\frac{v_p^2}{v_p'^2} - 1 \right)^2 dx = \min_0 \quad (9)$$

Supposing that the improved law of gravity and improved Newton's second law can be written as the following constant dimension fractal forms

$$F = -\frac{GMm}{r^D} \quad (10)$$

$$F = ma^{1+\varepsilon} \quad (11)$$

where: D and ε are constants.

Now we calculate the related quantities according to the law of conservation of energy. From Eq.(10), the potential energy of the small ball located at point P is

$$V = -\frac{GMm}{(D-1)r_{O'P}^{D-1}} \quad (12)$$

According to the law of conservation of energy, we can get

$$-\frac{GMm}{(D-1)r_{O'A}^{D-1}} = \frac{1}{2}mv_P'^2 - \frac{GMm}{(D-1)r_{O'P}^{D-1}} \quad (13)$$

And therefore

$$v_P'^2 = \frac{2GM}{D-1} \left[\frac{1}{r_{O'P}^{D-1}} - \frac{1}{(R+H)^{D-1}} \right] \quad (14)$$

Now we calculate the related quantities according to the improved law of gravity and improved Newton's second law. Supposing that the equation of rolling line is

$$y = x + H \quad (15)$$

For the ball located at point P,

$$dv/dt = a \quad (16)$$

because

$$dt = \frac{ds}{v} = \frac{\sqrt{2}dx}{v}$$

Therefore

$$vdv = a\sqrt{2}dx \quad (17)$$

According to the improved law of gravity, the force along to the tangent is

$$F_a = \frac{GMm}{r_{O'P}^D} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (18)$$

According to the improved Newton's second law, for point P, the acceleration along to the tangent is

$$a = \left(\frac{F_a}{m}\right)^{1/1+\varepsilon} = \left(\frac{GM}{r_{O'P}^D \sqrt{2}}\right)^{1/1+\varepsilon} \quad (19)$$

From Eq. (17) , it gives

$$vdv = \left\{ \frac{GM}{[(H+x)^2 + (R+H-y)^2]^{D/2} \sqrt{2}} \right\}^{1/1+\varepsilon} \sqrt{2}dx \quad (20)$$

Substituting Eq.(15) into Eq.(20), and for the two sides, we run the integral operation from A to P, it gives

$$v_P^2 = 2 \int_{-H}^{x_P} \left\{ \frac{GM}{[(H+x)^2 + (R-x)^2]^{D/2}} \right\}^{1/1+\varepsilon} (\sqrt{2})^{\varepsilon/1+\varepsilon} dx \quad (21)$$

then the value can be calculated by a method of numerical integral.

The given data are assumed to be: for Earth, $GM=3.99 \times 10^{14} \text{m}^3/\text{s}^2$; the radius of the Earth $R=6.37 \times 10^6 \text{m}$, $H=R/10$, try to solve the problem shown in Fig. 1, find the solution for the value of v_B^2 , and derive the improved law of gravity and the improved Newton's second law. Firstly, according to the original law of gravity, the original Newton's second law (i.e., let $D=2$ in Eq.(10), $\varepsilon=0$ in Eq.(11)) and the law of conservation of energy, all the related quantities can be calculated, then substitute them into Eq.(9), it gives

$$\Pi_0 = 571.4215$$

Here, according to the law of conservation of energy, it gives $v_B^2 = 1.0767 \times 10^7$, while according to the original law of gravity, and the original Newton's second law, it gives $v_B^2 = 1.1351 \times 10^7$, the difference is about 5.4 %.

For the reason that the value of Π_0 is not equal to zero, then the values of D and ε can be decided by the optimum seeking method. At present all the optimum seeking methods can be divided into two types, one type may not depend on the initial values which program may be complicated, and another type requires the better initial values which program is simple. One method of the second type, namely the searching method will be used in this paper.

Firstly, the value of D is fixed so let $D=2$, then search the value of ε , as $\varepsilon=0.0146$, the value of Π reaches the minimum 139.3429; then the value of ε is fixed, and search the value of D , as $D=1.99989$, the value of Π reaches the minimum 137.3238; then the value of D is fixed, and search the value of ε , as $\varepsilon=0.01458$, the value of Π reaches minimum 137.3231. Because the last two results are highly close, the searching can be stopped, and the final results are as follows

$$D=1.99989, \varepsilon=0.01458, \Pi=137.3231$$

Here the value of Π is only 24% of Π_0 . While according to the law of conservation of energy, it gives $v_B^2=1.0785 \times 10^7$, according to the improved law of gravity and the improved Newton's second law, it gives $v_B^2=1.1073 \times 10^7$, the difference is about 2.7% only.

The results suitable for this example with the constant dimension fractal form are as follows

The improved law of gravity reads

$$F = -\frac{GMm}{r^{1.99989}} \quad (22)$$

The improved Newton's second law reads

$$F = ma^{1.01458} \quad (23)$$

The above mentioned results have been published on reference [1].

According to the results for the example shown in Fig.1, it can be said that we could not rely on any experimental data, only apply the law of conservation of energy to derive the improved law of gravity, and improved Newton's second law; and demonstrate that the original Newton's law of gravity and Newton's second law are all tenable approximately for this example. So, can only apply the law of conservation of energy to derive that these two original laws or demonstrate they are tenable accurately in some cases? The answer is that in some cases we can indeed derive the original Newton's second law and prove the original Newton's law of gravity is tenable accurately.

Now, in the case that a small ball free falls (equivalent to free fall from A to C in Fig. 1), we derive the original Newton's second law and prove the original Newton's law of gravity is tenable accurately. Assuming that for the original law of gravity and Newton's second law, the related exponents are unknown, only know the forms of

these two formulas are as follows: $F = -\frac{GMm}{r^D}$,

$F = ma^{D'}$; where: D and D' are undetermined constants. As shown in Fig.1, supposing that a small ball free falls from point A to point C. Similar to the above derivation, when the small ball falls to point P (point P is not shown in Fig.1), the value of v_p^2 calculated by the undetermined Newton's second law and the law of gravity, as well as the value of v_p^2 calculated by the law of conservation of energy are as follows:

$$v_p^2 = \frac{2GM}{D-1} \left[\frac{1}{r_{OP}^{D-1}} - \frac{1}{(R+H)^{D-1}} \right]$$

$$v_p^2 = 2(GM)^{1/D'} \int_0^{y_p} (R+H-y)^{-D/D'} dy$$

$$v_p^2 = 2(GM)^{1/D'} \left\{ -\frac{1}{1-D/D'} [(R+H-y)^{1-D/D'}] \right\}_0^{y_p}$$

$$v_p^2 = \frac{2(GM)^{1/D'}}{(D/D')-1} \left[\frac{1}{r_{OP}^{(D/D')-1}} - \frac{1}{(R+H)^{(D/D')-1}} \right]$$

Let $v_p^2 = v_p^2$, then we should have: $1 = 1/D'$, and $D-1 = (D/D')-1$; these two equations all give: $D'=1$, this means that for free fall problem, by using the law of conservation of energy, we strictly derive the original Newton's second law $F = ma$.

Here, although the original law of gravity cannot be derived (the value of D may be any constant, certainly including the case that D=2), we already prove that the original law of gravity is not contradicted to the law of conservation of energy, or the original law of gravity is tenable accurately. For the example shown in Fig.1 that a small ball rolls along the inclined plane, in order to obtain the better results, we discuss the variable dimension fractal solution with Eq.(4) that is established by the law of conservation of energy directly.

Supposing that the improved Newton's second law and the improved law of gravity with the form of variable dimension fractal can be written as follows:

$$F = ma^{1+\varepsilon}, \varepsilon = k_1 u; F = -GMm/r^{2-\delta},$$

$\delta = k_2 u$; where: u is the horizon distance that the small ball rolls ($u = x + H$).

With the similar searching method, the values of k_1, k_2 can be determined, and the results are as follows

$$\varepsilon = 8.85 \times 10^{-8} u, \quad \delta = 2.71 \times 10^{-13} u$$

The results of variable dimension fractal are much better than that of constant dimension fractal. For example, the final $\Pi = 5.8662 \times 10^{-4}$, it is only 0.019% of Π_0 (3.1207). While according to the law of conservation of energy, it gives $v_B^2 = 1.0767 \times 10^7$, according to the improved law of gravity and the improved Newton's second law, it gives $v_B^2 = 1.0777 \times 10^7$, the difference is about 0.093 % only. The results suitable for this example with the variable dimension fractal form are as follows

The improved law of gravity reads

$$F = -\frac{GMm}{r^{2-2.71 \times 10^{-13} u}} \quad (24)$$

The improved Newton's second law reads

$$F = ma^{1+8.85 \times 10^{-8} u} \quad (25)$$

where: u is the horizon distance that the small ball rolls ($u = x + H$)

There is another problem should also be discussed. That is the improved kinetic energy formula. As well-known, the kinetic energy formula has been modified in the theory of relativity, now we improve the kinetic energy formula with the law of conservation of energy.

Supposing that the improved kinetic energy formula is

$$E_d = \frac{1}{2} m v^{2-\lambda}, \quad \lambda = k_3 u; \quad \text{where: } u \text{ is the horizon distance that the small ball rolls } (u = x + H).$$

With the similar searching method, we can get:

$k_3 = 9.95 \times 10^{-13}$, then the improved kinetic energy formula with variable dimension fractal form reads

$$E_d = \frac{1}{2} m v^{2-9.95 \times 10^{-13} u}$$

Because the effect of improvement is very small (the value of Π is only improved from 5.8662×10^{-4} into 5.8634×10^{-4}), therefore these results should be for reference only.

3 With the help of general relativity and accurate experimental data to derive the improved Newton's formula of universal gravitation

We already point out that, according to Neutrosophy and Quad-stage Method, various results can be reached. Prof. Hu Ning derived an equation according to general relativity, with the help of Hu's equation and Binet's formula, we get the following improved Newton's formula of universal gravitation^[2]

$$F = -\frac{GMm}{r^2} - \frac{3G^2 M^2 m p}{c^2 r^4} \quad (26)$$

where: G is gravitational constant, M and m are the masses of the two objects, r is the distance between the two objects, c is the speed of light, p is the half normal chord for the object m moving around the object M along with a curve, and the value of p is given by: $p = a(1-e^2)$ (for ellipse), $p = a(e^2-1)$ (for hyperbola), $p = y^2/2x$ (for parabola).

It should be noted that, this improved Newton's formula of universal gravitation can also be written as the form of variable dimension fractal.

Suppose

$$-\frac{GMm}{r^D} = -\frac{GMm}{r^2} - \frac{3G^2 M^2 m p}{c^2 r^4}$$

$$\text{It gives } D = -\ln\left(\frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{3GMp}{c^2 r^4}\right) / \ln r$$

For the problem of gravitational deflection of a photon orbit around the Sun, $M=1.99 \times 10^{30} \text{kg}$, $r_0=6.96 \times 10^8 \text{m}$, $c=2.9979 \times 10^8 \text{m/s}$, then we have: $1.954997 \leq D \leq 2$.

The improved Newton's universal gravitation formula (Eq.(26)) can give the same results as given by general relativity for the problem of planetary advance of perihelion and the problem of gravitational deflection of a photon orbit around the Sun.

For the problem of planetary advance of perihelion, the improved Newton's universal gravitation formula reads

$$F = -\frac{GMm}{r^2} - \frac{3G^2M^2ma(1-e^2)}{c^2r^4} \quad (27)$$

For the problem of gravitational defection of a photon orbit around the Sun, the improved Newton's universal gravitation formula reads

$$F = -\frac{GMm}{r^2} - \frac{1.5GMmr_0^2}{r^4} \quad (28)$$

where : r_0 is the shortest distance between the light and the Sun, if the light and the Sun is tangent, it is equal to the radius of the Sun.

The funny thing is that, for this problem, the maximum gravitational force given by the improved Newton's universal gravitation formula is 2.5 times of that given by the original Newton's law of gravity.

Although the deflection angles given by Eq.(26) and Eq.(28) are all exactly the same as given by general relativity, they have still slight deviations with the precise astronomical observations. What are the reasons? According to "universal relations", the answer is that the deflection angle not only is depended on the gravitational effect of the Sun, but also depended on the gravitational effects of other celestial bodies, as well as the influences of sunlight pressure and so on. If all factors are taken into account, not only general relativity can do nothing for this problem, but also for a long time it could not be solved by theoretical method. Therefore, at present the only way to solve this problem is based on the precise observations to derive the synthesized gravitational formula (including the effects of other celestial bodies and sunlight pressure) for the problem of deflection of photon around the Sun.

As well-known, the deflection angle ϕ_0 given by general relativity or the improved Newton's formula of universal gravitation is as follows

$$\phi_0 = 1.75''$$

Adding an additional term to Eq.(28), it gives the synthesized gravitational formula between the photon and the Sun as follows

$$F = -\frac{GMm}{r^2} \left(1 + \frac{3GMp}{c^2r^2} + \frac{wG^2M^2p^2}{c^4r^4} \right) \quad (29)$$

where: w is a constant to be determined.

Now we determine the value of w according to accurate experimental data. Firstly the problem of deflection of photon around the Sun as shown in Fig.2 will be solved with Eq.(29). The method to be used is the same as presented in references [2] and [3].

Fig. 2 Deflection of photon around the Sun

Supposing that m represents the mass of photon. Because the deflection angle is very small, we can assume that $x=r_0$; thus on point (x, y), its coordinate can be written as (r_0, y) , then the force acted on photon reads

$$F_x = \frac{Fr_0}{(r_0^2 + y^2)^{1/2}} \quad (30)$$

where : The value of F is given by Eq.(29).

Because

$$mv_x = \int F_x dt = \int F_x \frac{dy}{v_y} \approx \frac{1}{c} \int F_x dy \quad (31)$$

Hence

$$v_x \approx -\frac{2GMr_0}{c} \int_0^\infty \frac{dy}{(r_0^2 + y^2)^{3/2}} - \frac{6G^2M^2pr_0}{c^3} \int_0^\infty \frac{dy}{(r_0^2 + y^2)^{5/2}} - \frac{2wG^3M^3p^2r_0}{c^5} \int_0^\infty \frac{dy}{(r_0^2 + y^2)^{7/2}} \quad (32)$$

Because

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{dy}{(r_0^2 + y^2)^{3/2}} = \frac{1}{r_0^2}, \quad \int_0^\infty \frac{dy}{(r_0^2 + y^2)^{5/2}} = \frac{2}{3r_0^4},$$

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{dy}{(r_0^2 + y^2)^{7/2}} = \frac{8}{15r_0^6}$$

Therefore

$$v_x \approx -\frac{2GM}{cr_0} - \frac{4G^2 M^2 p}{c^3 r_0^3} - \frac{16wG^3 M^3 p^2}{15c^5 r_0^5}$$

Because

$$\phi \approx tg\phi \approx \frac{|v_x|}{c}$$

By using the half normal chord given in reference [2], it gives

$$p = \frac{c^2 r_0^2}{2GM}$$

Then the deflection angle is as follows

$$\phi = \frac{4GM}{c^2 r_0} \left| 1 + \frac{w}{15} \right| \tag{33}$$

where: r_0 is the radius of Sun. Because

$$\phi_0 = \frac{4GM}{c^2 r_0} \tag{34}$$

Then, it gives

$$\phi = \phi_0 \left(1 + \frac{w}{15} \right) \tag{35}$$

Thus the value of w can be solved as follows

$$w = 15 \left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_0} - 1 \right) \tag{36}$$

Now we can determine the value of w according to the experimental data.

Table 1 shows the experimental data of radio astronomy for the deflection angle of photon around the Sun (taken from reference [4]).

Table 1. The experimental data of radio astronomy for the deflection angle of photon around the Sun

Year	Observer	Observed value / ''
1969	G.A.Seielstud et al	1.77±0.20
1969	D.O.Muhleman et al	1.82 ^{+0.24} _{-0.17}
1969	I.I.Shapiro	1.80±0.2
1970	R.A.Sramak	1.57±0.08
1970	J.M.Hill	1.87±0.3
1972		1.82±0.14
1974		1.73±0.05
1975		1.78±0.02

Now we choose the experimental data in 1975, it gives

$$1.76 \leq \phi \leq 1.80$$

Then, we have

$$0.08571 \leq w \leq 0.42857$$

Taking the average value, it gives

$$w=0.25714$$

Thus, according to the experimental data, the synthesized gravitational formula can be decided.

4 Contradiction between the law of conservation of energy and the law of conservation of momentum as well as the law of conservation of angular momentum

According to Neutrosophy, any law may be in three states: correct, wrong, and it is correct under certain conditions.

As well-known, unlike the law of conservation of energy, the law of conservation of momentum and the law of conservation of angular momentum are only correct under

certain conditions. For example, considering friction force and the like, these two laws will not be correct.

Now we point out further that for NNM the law of conservation of momentum as well as the law of conservation of angular momentum will be not correct under certain conditions (or their results contradict with the law of conservation of energy). As well-known, in order to prove the law of conservation of momentum as well as the law of conservation of angular momentum, the original Newton's second law should be applied. However, as we have made clear, the original Newton's second law will not be correct under certain conditions, for such cases, these two laws also will not correct.

Here we find another problem, if the original three conservation laws are all correct, therefore for certain issues, the law of conservation of energy and the other two conservation laws could be combined to apply. While for NNM, if the other two conservation laws cannot be applied, how to complement the new formulas to replace these two conservation laws? The solution is very simple: according to the law of conservation of energy, for any time, the derivatives of total energy $W(t)$ should be all equal to zero, then we have

$$\frac{d^n W(t)}{dt^n} = 0 \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (37)$$

In addition, running the integral operations to the both sides of Eq.(3), it gives

$$W(0)t = \int_0^t W(t)dt \quad (38)$$

Now we illustrate that, because there is one truth only, even within the scope of original classical mechanics, the contradiction could also appear between the law of conservation of energy and the law of conservation of momentum.

As shown in Fig.3, a man walks along the car located on the horizontal smooth rail, the length of the car equals L , the mass of the man is m_1 and the car is m_2 . At beginning the man and the car are all at rest, then the man walks from one end to the other end of the car, try to decide the moving distances of the man and the car. This example is taken from references [5].

Fig.3 A man walks along the car located on the horizontal smooth rail.

As solving this problem by using the original classical mechanics, the law of conservation of momentum will be used, it gives

$$m_1 v_1 + m_2 v_2 = 0$$

However, at beginning the man and the car are all at rest, the total energy of the system is equal to zero; while once they are moving, they will have speeds, and the total energy of the system is not equal to zero; thus the law of conservation of energy will be destroyed. For this paradox, the original classical mechanics looks without seeing. In fact, considering the lost energy of the man and applying the law of conservation of energy, the completely different result will be reached.

As the original law of conservation of momentum ($P_t = P_0 = Const$) and the law of conservation of angular momentum ($L_t = L_0 = Const$) are not correct, we can propose their improved forms of variable dimension fractal. The improved law of conservation of momentum: $P_t = P_0^{1+\delta}$ (δ is a constant or a variable), and the improved law of conservation of angular momentum: $L_t = L_0^{1+\varepsilon}$ (ε is a constant or a variable).

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